

ANNEX 1: NEIGHBORHOOD TYPOLOGIES

A deep dive into neighborhood typologies

Instead of mapping a single characteristic (e.g. green space), we can create composite maps in which we combine a set of different characteristics to create neighborhood typologies. Different neighborhoods have different unique characteristics. Therefore, each neighborhood has a unique role to play in the city-wide transition to a circular economy. For example, we can design outer city neighborhoods to produce excess renewable energy serving the entire city as production centers by building upon their (post-) industrial nature, proximity to natural resources, and existing infrastructure. In contrast, high-density neighborhoods in a city-center might be a more suitable location to spark circular innovation and entrepreneurship, as well as provide residents with many of the cultural and commercial functions that are essential to any city.

By collecting a suite of geospatial layers into a single composite map, we can generate a deeper understanding of these different roles that neighborhoods can play- we can create “neighborhood typologies”. The following characteristics provide an interesting starting point for identifying the role that a neighborhood can play in the transition:

- Population density
- (Nearby) infrastructure (e.g. roads, waterways, and railways; waste processing sites; distribution centers)
- Land use (e.g. industrial activity; agricultural land; commercial area; residential area)
- Density and type of services (e.g. shops; healthcare centers; commercial parties)

The map on the following page shows an example of a neighborhood typology map for the city of Amsterdam. The map uses the above-mentioned characteristics to identify the role that the city's different neighborhoods could potentially play in relation to material resources cycling.

Neighborhood Typologies in the city of Amsterdam (the Netherlands)

Consumption center

These areas are characterized by a **high population density** and typically smaller houses that **lack space for extensive recycling infrastructure**.

Transit neighborhoods

The **peri-central location** of these neighborhoods and **relatively open spatial layout** makes them potentially suitable to fulfill a nodal function in the transportation and distribution of resources. They can serve as transit points to streamline waste collection and the exchange of products, as sites of experimentation and new circular entrepreneurship.

Loop closers

Marked by a **low population density** and the **proximity of recycling centers**, these neighborhoods can play a vital role in closing resource cycles on a local scale. By processing waste flows that will increase in quality over the coming years, these neighborhoods can become future sites of production.

Innovation neighborhoods

Due to these neighborhoods' **peri-central location** in combination with a relatively **high density of services and mixed-use areas**, they can be developed as sites of experimentation and new circular entrepreneurship. They form a crucial bridge between the outward most recycling centres and the urban communities in the center.

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Figure 32. Neighborhood typologies in the city of Amsterdam. Source: Metabolic, 2017.

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ANNEX 2: OVERVIEW TABLE OF GEOSPATIAL LAYERS				

Table 5. Template for selected geospatial context information

CATEGORY	GEOSPATIAL CONTEXT INFORMATION	POTENTIAL SOURCE	ASSIGNED DATA CHAMPION
Recommended layers	Population density	Municipality	<i>[fill in name of assigned data champion]</i>
	Land use (e.g. built environment, grassland, forest)	Open Street Map	
	Infrastructure (e.g. roads, ports, airports, waste treatment plants)	OpenStreetMap/ Google Maps API	
Urban nature	<i>[fill in selected layer]</i>	<i>[potential source]</i>	
Urban communities			
Urban industries			

ANNEX 3: CENTRINNO DATA REQUEST TEMPLATE

CENTRINNO data request [template]

Gathering urban data

Introduction

As part of the EU funded CENTRINNO research project, we are working on developing strategies for inclusive, circular and sustainable urban regeneration in nine historical industrial sites all over Europe. One of CENTRINNO's core objectives is to support (post-)industrial districts to once again become thriving centers of creative making, urban manufacturing and productivity.

The [XYZ neighborhood/site, in city XYZ] is one of the nine pilot sites in this project. As [insert brief description of your own organization], in collaboration with a global consortium of 25 knowledge institutions, we are currently conducting a set of analyses to gain a better understanding of the site and the surrounding city from a socio-economic, ecological and economic perspective.

We are sending out this data request sheet to collect relevant datasets for conducting our analyses. We are collecting datasets along two major categories:

Geospatial context analysis

Material flow analysis

For both of these categories the requested datasets are listed in the tables below.

Reference year and geographic scope

For our analysis, we will use data from the year 2019. If data from 2019 is not available, we would like to receive the most recent available dataset (e.g. 2017). The scope of the data is the municipal city boundaries: the municipality of [city].

Questions and comments

Within [name of your organisation], the following contact person is available for questions or comments regarding the data request:

[insert name of data champion] [insert phone #] [insert email]

1. Geospatial context analysis data

We are performing a geospatial context analysis at the neighborhood level, which allows us to identify the role that different neighborhoods can play in the transition to a circular economy. We would like to receive the following data **for each of the city's administrative neighborhoods. If data is not available at the neighborhood level, we would appreciate any city-level data.**

Data format

There is a range of different data formats. Data can be delivered in any of the following formats, as long as it specifies the data at the level of the individual neighborhood.

- **List or table:** Data can be provided through lists that present data at the neighborhood level.
- **Geospatial files**, such as .geojson; .gpkg; .gml; .kml; .shp; .csv (with specification of the used coordinate system); .SQLite; .OSM; .tif; .tiff; .GTiff; .IMG; .ASC.

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2. Material flow analysis data

To work towards a circular economy, it is important to have insight on how resources flow through the city. Through a material flow analysis, we're identifying what resources flow through the city, how much (quantity), and how the resources are used in the city. In the CENTRINNO project, we're focussing on the flow of waste streams, as these can potentially be used as secondary resources for new products. To do this calculation, we need the following data. Once again the preferred scale of data is at the neighborhood level. However, it is possible that data is not always available at this granular level. If data is not available at the level of individual neighborhoods, we'd love to receive the data at closest scale possible.

Requested datasets

Table 6. Data request template for geospatial context information

DATA DESCRIPTION	UNIT	PREFERRED SCALE
Population	#- number of residents per neighborhood	Neighborhood level
Average Median Income	€- per capita median income, per neighborhood	Neighborhood level
Demographic distribution	#- Number per age per sex	Neighborhood level
Employment rate	%	Neighborhood level
Land ownership	Geospatial map with descriptions (e.g. "public", "private")	Plot level
Total employment in different sectors	#- Number of employees per economic activity	Neighborhood level
Housing prices	€- per square meter	Individual Housing plots
<i>(additional data layers, as defined by pilots)</i>		

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Requested datasets

Table 7. Data request template for material flow analysis

DATA DESCRIPTION	UNIT	PREFERRED SCALE
Waste flows		
Total amount of municipally managed waste	tons	City-wide
Composition of municipally managed waste	% plastic, % paper, % glass, etc.	City-wide
Amount sent to recycling per waste stream	tons	
Amount sent to incineration per waste stream	tons	
Amount sent to landfill per waste stream	tons	
Amount of waste composted	tons	
Waste management infrastructure		
Municipally contracted waste handlers	Contact, address	City-wide
Private waste handlers	List of registered private waste haulers	City-wide
Waste pre-sorting and sorting facilities	Location, name, amount and composition of waste sorted in this facility	City-wide
Recycling stations	Location, name and waste data (see under "waste flows")	City-wide
Waste incineration plants	Location, name, amount and type of incinerated waste	City-wide
Waste collection bins	Location and type of bin (e.g. glass, textiles, plastics)	City-wide

Thank you for filling in this data request sheet. We appreciate your time and effort!

ANNEX 4: STAKEHOLDER SURVEY TEMPLATE

Worksheet – Designing a stakeholder survey.

Table 8. Stakeholder survey template

1. CENTRINNO INTRODUCTION	
Provide a description of:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Your pilot • The CENTRINNO Project • The CENTRINNO Cartography • Why you are doing this survey
2. GENERAL INFORMATION	
Standard Industrial Classification Code	
General activity description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabricator • Material Supplier • Workshop Facility • School • Community Organization • Etc.
Company size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of employees
Who the company works with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large businesses • SMEs • Individual professions • Students • General public
3. FIVE BUILDING BLOCKS FOR RESOURCES INVENTORIES	
<p>Block 1: Waste Inventories (Resources in urban industries) <i>A set of questions about waste resources and materials that are used by local industries & businesses. This building block is relevant to all stakeholders that may generate larger volumes of homogenous wastes that could be reused as a feedstock by local artisans and makers. Examples are SMEs, industrial facilities, restaurants, supermarkets. You can tailor these details of these questions to either broadly investigate what is in your area, or ask for the availability of specific waste streams.</i></p>	
<p>Scenario 1: We just want to get a broad overview of waste</p>	<p>What type of clean, large-volume waste streams are you generating (per year)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed food waste; homogenous food waste; wood waste; agricultural waste; textile waste; etc. • Specify waste type and its estimated amount • Waste treatment options/ waste collector <p>Would you be willing to donate waste resources to other makers/ SMEs/ training programs/ workshops?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes (please specify) • No (please specify) • I need more information (please specify)
<p>Scenario 2: We already know the types of materials we are looking for</p>	<p>What type of clean, large-volume waste streams that you are generating (per year)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saw dust; wood chips; pallet waste; untreated scrap wood; laminated wood; etc. • Specify waste type and its estimated amount • Waste treatment options

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Would you be willing to donate waste resources to other makers/ SMEs/ training programs/ workshops?

- Yes (please specify)
- No (please specify)
- I need more information (please specify)

Block 2: Technology and Tools Inventory (Resources in urban industries)

A set of questions about tools, technology and processing capacity available at organizations. This building block is especially relevant to capture specific technical assets that local businesses, manufacturers, research institutions or community maker spaces. Examples of elements in this building block may be digital technologies (3D printers, laser cutters, etc.), bio refining technologies or other material-specific processing equipment. In addition, low-tech tools or technology may be inventoried: innovative composting technologies. Resources and inspirations for tools, processes and machines can be found under [Open Workshop Network](#) or [Make.Works](#).

Which advanced manufacturing technologies do you use in your organization?

Brainstorm advanced manufacturing technologies you may need.

Examples of digital and advanced technologies that could be covered:

- 3D printing
- Laser cutting
- 3D scanning
- Digital weaving machines

Which machines and tools do you work with?

Brainstorm machines and tools you may need.

Example Textile Sector:

- Industrial sewing machines
- Knitting machine
- Upholstery machines
- Upholstery hand tools
- Weaving machine

Examples Agrifood Sector:

- Tracking or tracing technologies
- Smart farming tools
- Bio refining technologies
- Composting technologies

Which materials do you work with?

Brainstorm materials you may want to take stock of.

- Ceramics (please specify)
- Plastics (please specify)
- Wood (please specify)
- Steel (please specify)
- Bio-materials (please specify)

Block 3: Skills & Knowledge Inventory (Resources in urban communities)

A set of questions that cover skills, knowledge and other human capital “assets” present in local organizations or even individuals. This building block is relevant to capture those intangible resources that may be important to transition towards a locally productive, sustainable and circular city while respecting traditional knowledge. There will be some overlaps with Block 2: Technologies & Tools since we can also consider it a “skill” to use a certain tool or machine.

Scenario 1: We just want to get a broad overview of skills and knowledge

Which services does your organization offer?

Which skills does your organization teach or cultivate?

(insert a multiple choice list of broader categories of skills or knowledge interesting to you)

Scenario 2: We know what we are looking for

Are you familiar with any of the following skills?

Example activities for Agrifood Sector:

- Building local composting platforms
- Knowledge about growing heritage crops
- Knowledge about alternative farming practices

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Example activities for Agrifood Sector:

- Building local composting platforms
- Knowledge about growing heritage crops
- Knowledge about alternative farming practices

Would you be willing to share these skills/ knowledge with others?

- Yes (please specify)
- No
- I need more information

If yes, how will you share these skills/ knowledge with others? (Please specify)

Block 4: Community Services Inventory (Resources in urban communities)

A set of questions to take stock of services offered around pilot sites. Pilots are encouraged to start with scoping out what type of services are relevant to their activities in order to create a better sense of which questions to ask. We think it is useful to distinguish between two scenarios: (1) pilots who are still at their starting point may and (2) pilots who are looking to map very specific services.

Scenario 1: We just want to get a broad overview of skills and knowledge

Which services does your organization offer?

(Insert a multiple choice list of broader service categories interesting for you, but also leave space to fill in services)

- Crafts and repair
- Entertainment, culture, sports
- Education and apprenticeships
- Public health services
- Social welfare services
- Scientific & research services
- Internships (specify how often and for which audience)
- Space (storage space, workshop space...)
- Logistics and transport

Scenario 2: We know which services we are looking for across our site (and beyond)

Which specific services does your organization offer?

(Draft out a specific list of services in the sectors you are interested in)

Example services for craftsmanship sector:

- Training services for local wood workers
- Internships offers in woodworking industry

Example activities for culture & heritage sector:

- Building capacity for cultural tourist management
- Building capacity on preserving heritage buildings

Example activities for education sector:

- Training on specific local arts/ fashion/ textile
- Knowledge about business development on the product

Would you be willing to offer your services to [insert your target audience] or list your services in the CENTRINNO Cartography?

- Yes (please specify)
- No
- I need more information

If yes, how could you share these services with others?
(Please specify)

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Block 5: Natural resources inventory (Resources in urban nature)

A set of questions that identify natural resources that cannot be easily mapped through top-down geospatial data collection. This building block can either identify biophysical resources, such as local compost, heritage crops, or pollinator-friendly urban spaces, or it can go a step further and map socio-ecological values, attitudes and knowledge on sustainable natural resources management. To support the mapping of values and attitudes towards natural spaces in cities, participatory tools like maptionnaire can help to engage local communities by building map-based surveys that crowdsource spatial data.

Biophysical resources

Which natural resources and biomaterials do you have access to? [in your garden, farm, etc]

(Examples of biological resources you may ask for)

- Pruning waste
- Compost
- Mulch
- Heritage crops & seeds
- Produce (please specify)
- Livestock (please specify)

“Socio-ecological knowledge”

Do you have experience with...

(Examples of socio-ecological knowledge you may ask for)

- Farming and gardening practices (agroforestry, permaculture, integrated grazing)
- Composting and soil remediation
- (Traditional) culinary practices (food preparation, preserving, canning)
- *Add practices interesting for you*

Values to land and local nature

Mapping the attitudes of people to natural spaces in their surrounding helps us to understand what value service a park, river or local “abandoned” brownfield may or may not provide. For example, on paper, an area may be full of green spaces but if these spaces do not feel safe to a community, they will not provide the recreational value that is usually assigned to them.

To support the mapping of values and attitudes towards natural spaces in cities, participatory tools like maptionnaire can help to engage local communities by building map-based surveys that crowdsource spatial data.

4. JOINING THE CENTRINNO CARTOGRAPHY

Each survey should end with a few questions that clarify how the collected data may be used for the Cartography. Do they agree to share their organization’s name and contact info on the website to enable others to reach out to them, if interested in reusing or making use of resources? Or do they just agree to share their data anonymized? Other possible questions in this section could raise attention about some of the other CENTRINNO activities and potential involvement opportunities for local organization.

Agreement to use information in CENTRINNO Cartography

If they agree to share their details, ask for business name, contact and address (either personalized or anonymized)

Availability for follow-up questions

Attention to join other CENTRINNO Activities

- Participation in CENTRINNO Networking activities
- Participation in emotion networking workshops
- Contribution to the Living Archive with a story, memory, photo about a specific heritage item

ANNEX 5: HOW TO EMOTION NETWORK

HOW TO EMOTION NETWORK?

A preliminary course structure for CENTRINNO pilots

By: Hester Dibbits (Reinwardt Academie, AHK); Jonathan Even-Zohar (Reinwardt Academie, AHK); Danielle Kuijten (Imagine IC); Eline Minnaar-Kuiper (Imagine IC); with a contribution on communication and emotions by Amanda Diemel (Amazon Counsel)

1. Course structure

In this section we present a preliminary course on emotion networking. This course is used in the CENTRINNO to project, and will be adapted to local conditions in its usage and delivery. After each sprint, it will be modified and updated to accommodate all the learnings.

1.1 Purpose

The course is meant for CENTRINNO Pilot Leaders, in particular to the project partners' staff who will use emotion networking in their local pilot.

1.2 Aims

The course will provide the participants with:

- Gained **insights** into the vision on dynamics in culture and heritage on which the method of emotion networking is based,
- Gained insights into using emotion networks and the dynamic of conversation to map and understand how an item/object/location of heritage is understood/felt/perceived by different stakeholders (in the broadest sense)
- Built **capacities** to lead the implementation of emotion networking in the CENTRINNO pilots
- Practical **information** on optimal ways of gathering data, relevant and tailored to local pilot contexts (e.g. photo-voices, mapping, etc.)

Specific learning outcomes:

- Shared perspective on heritage dynamics
- Facilitation techniques
- Communication skills
- Conflict mitigation/adaptation
- Heritage networking skills

1.3 Set-up

This course is an adaptive modular course. For each pilot a set of sessions can be tailor-made. Each session lasts 2 x 45 minutes. All sessions are done online, using Zoom. In addition, we are looking at preparing more guidance material, which could include reading as well as short video instructions. All this is done in such a way that the course can be used for further training to third parties during the project.

1.3.1 Sessions

- 1. Orientation/take-in:** This first session gives us the opportunity to get an initial understanding of the contact and challenge as to why and how the pilot leaders would seek to implement emotion networking.
- 2. Trialing the method and exploration/mapping of possible participants:** The second session allows us to demonstrate how emotion networking works, and to map out and agree on what steps the pilot partners could take to prepare their own sessions.
 - » Following this session, pilots are asked to conduct their own experiments with the session and identify who they seek to take the role of facilitator.
- 3. Training:** The third session is where we provide the full training on how the pilot partners can go ahead to start using the emotion networking method in their own context. Hereby are included presentations of the initial tools needed to conduct sessions locally and open discussion (Q&A) about adaptability.

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1.3.2 Trainers

Depending on availability the training sessions will be facilitated by practitioners of Imagine IC and Reinwardt Academy (AHK).

2. Tools

This section presents the initially available tools for pilot organisers of emotion networking sessions, including (1) detailed implementation plan and (2) facilitators' guide with a focus on non-violent communication.

2.1 Detailed implementation plan

2.1.1 Prepare

In preparation of an emotion networking session, you will need to gain a sense of what is going at the site. To this aim, take enough time to get well acquainted with the site as an ethnologist or anthropologist would do, i.e. take time for intensive and ongoing immersion through physical presence and participation in day-to-day life, experiencing and recording of what is going on (Schmidt-Lauber, 2012). Nose around, talk to people, go out for observational walks, make mental maps, use all your senses while doing site research.

As a next step, select with your pilot team one or more elements or aspects of the **industrial historical site** that you, your pilot team or others want to qualify (and showcase) as "heritage", i.e. as something from an imagined past that should be passed on as useful to an imagined future.

This selection is made for strategic reasons, with the general aim of showcasing the potential of the site to become inclusive hubs of entrepreneurship. By making the selection in advance, you become a heritage curator: it is you (or your team) who foregrounds the specific element as an item of heritage. The element is instrumentalized for YOUR specific aims. It is YOUR choice.

In the process of selection, it may help to creatively work with / elaborate on the key messages, developed to clearly communicate the objectives, aims and focus of CENTRINNO. These messages target audiences and are both practical and aspirational. Thus, keeping in mind that CENTRINNO approaches heritage as a catalyst for innovation and social inclusion, ask yourself: how can the selected item of heritage be(come) a catalyst for innovation and social inclusion?

2.1.2 Invite participants for a session

Once you have an initial idea of what is going on at the site, and what the emotion network session should focus on, you can start to think of whom to invite for the session. The more diverse your group of participants is, the better. In the invitation, it should be made clear that the invitees take part not as a representative of a group, but on a personal basis. Groups of 10+ participants can be split, but you will need additional moderators to facilitate with smaller groups.

2.1.3 The session: two formats

There are several possible formats that can be used for an emotion networking session. Below are the detailed instructions for two such formats:

A. one in which participants position themselves around a large sheet of paper and B. one in which participants position themselves in a room, or outdoors, close to (elements of) the item of heritage that will be the focus of the conversation.

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Table 9. Description of emotion networking sessions

FORMAT	A. Participants position themselves around a large sheet of paper.	B. Participants position themselves, in a room or outdoors, close to (elements of) the item of heritage that will be the focus of the conversation.
REQUIREMENTS	<p>A large sheet of paper, markers in various colors, a heritage item and background information about the object or the subject.</p> <p>Emotion scheme: Copy the emotion scheme from below and write or draw the object or the subject in the middle of the sheet.</p>	<p>A plinth (or similar basis on which an object can stand), various emoji's, an object and a variety of meanings connected to the object (e.g. information sheets, short videos, visual aids).</p> <p>In case the object is immaterial (e.g. a city area), use a visual representation to put it in the center.</p> <p>Put all requirements in the workshop space. Place the object on the plinth and make sure that there is enough space to be able for all participants to stand around it.</p>
START	<p>First ask the participants, as a way of understanding where everybody is at the start, the following question. Have everybody write their number on a piece of paper, which they can keep during the session:</p> <p>How aware do you consider yourself of the different emotions related to items of heritage (tangible and intangible) at this location?</p> <p>(1) Poor (2) Fair (3) Average (4) Good (5) Very good</p>	
STEP 1	Ask the group which emotions the item evokes. Request the participants to write (in silence) their emotions on the emotion scheme, with their initials and number 1 - close-by or far from the middle, depending on the intensity of the feeling(s).	Stand around the object. Ask the participants to express their feelings about the object in one or more emoji's. Ask them to position their chosen emoji's. Nearby = strong feelings. Distanced = less strong feelings.
STEP 2	Invite the participants, in case they want to, to elaborate on their chosen position and their feeling(s).	
STEP 3	Ask the participants to re-think and re-determine their position on the emotion-scheme with their initials and number 2, by drawing a line from their former position to their second position through the person who brought about the changes. Invite everybody to discuss these new positions.	Ask the participants if their feelings have changed. If this is the case, ask them to adjust the emoji's to their changed feelings. If feelings have not changed, the emoji can remain where they are. Invite participants, in case they want to, to elaborate their (un)changed position and feelings.
STEP 4	Share the information which was gathered in advance with the participants and provide them with sufficient time to read and/or view the different perspectives.	
STEP 5	Ask the participants after this intervention to decide again what their position is, using their initials and number 3, by drawing a line between numbers 2 and 3. Invite everybody to discuss these changes.	Go back to the subject. Ask the participants if their feelings have changed after step 3 and after step 4. If this is the case, ask them to adjust the emoji's to their changed feelings. If feelings have not changed, the emoji can remain where they are. Invite participants, in case they want to, to elaborate their (un)changed position and feelings.

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STEP 6	Ask the participants to place as many as possible stakeholders in the emotion network. Discuss together how this step influences the network.			
END	Remind the participants of the earlier question (below), and ask them to write down their number response again. Gather the papers at the end of the session. How aware do you consider yourself of the different emotions at this location? (1) Poor (2) Fair (3) Average (4) Good (5) Very good			
CLOSURE	Discuss the emotion network with the participants and summarise the changes which have taken place.			

2.2 Facilitator's guide with a focus on communication and emotions

by Amanda Diemel

As a facilitator it is important to keep in mind that heritage is not a given, but a construct. It is the preliminary result of a complicated process of negotiation, appreciation and selection, which involves power relations and many other factors, including some very practical ones. Heritage is a potential source of contestation because it forms part of a process of identity construction.

Heritage engenders the formation of networks consisting of people with wide-ranging emotions, including subdued, unuttered emotions. All sorts of people form part of such 'emotion networks', including you as a facilitator. The way we think about heritage, or what we consider to be heritage, is in part determined by our upbringing. Keep this in mind, before, during, and after a session.

As a facilitator it is your responsibility to provide a safe climate for conversation in which participants:

- dare to express their viewpoint
- respect each other
- listen and are listened to
- are open to taking up new positions/points of view

By offering clear "game rules" as a facilitator, you stimulate an environment in which you can create this safety together.

By participating in an emotion network session, people open themselves up to contact with viewpoints other than their own. Appreciate the fact that they are willing to look at the world through other people's eyes. Eyes that might frighten them, anger them or otherwise get to them in the first place. But only in this way new visions on heritage emerge and bridges are built.

There are three phases in which you, together with your participants, should pay attention to the 'how': the introductory phase, the main phase and the concluding phase of your meeting.

2.2.1 Phase 1. Introduction

In the introductory phase, you take the group into the 'why' of the meeting. You let them know that they are here together to enter each other's world through a specific theme. And that they need to be prepared to let themselves be moved by each other. Make clear that they don't have to agree with each other, but that they can feel free to change their own viewpoint as well.

Depending on the nature and potential 'danger' of the subject, **you can choose to draw up a few basic rules together with the group.** Ask the participants:

What do you need to feel safe so that you can express your point of view?

The first group rules can be listed by the group itself instead of you imposing them upon the group.

Once these have been established and accepted by the group, you yourself go into the importance of an open attitude while listening to each other. I will describe the tools for this below.

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Emotions make listening with an open mind challenging.

Emotion networks, the name says it all: emotions will play a role in the topics discussed. This makes it more difficult to listen openly to each other. It is important that your participants are aware of this, because by being aware they can do something with it instead of being overwhelmed by it.

Listening is not a passive act but an active act.

We often listen in order to react. Someone starts saying something and immediately you are forming a reaction in your head. Often, you do not really hear what is being said anymore.

Therefore, tell your participants to keep the **following elements** in mind while listening to each other:

- Be curious/interested in what the other person is saying.
- Be aware of your own viewpoint in relation to what the other person is saying.
- Be aware of the emotions that you might feel when listening.
- Do not condemn these emotions, nor instantly interact upon them.
- Check by means of open questions whether you really understand what the other person is saying.

As a moderator, it is important to consider the last two points in more detail. This is what people often find difficult. And where discussions can get out of hand.

If you are moved by what someone says, you move, as it were, from your rational, developed brain to your more primitive brain; the brain that wants to fight or flee when threatened. That makes it difficult to still be open to the other person.

What do you do when someone gets to you with what they say?

- Don't push it away because what you push away only gets stronger.
- Don't judge yourself for it: allow it to 'be', it obviously wants to tell you something.
- Identify what is happening to yourself so that you can talk about it.

Open questions are important. A suggestive question can make the other person respond defensively, feeling criticised or ridiculed. An open question gives you and the other person the space to exchange thoughts with each other in an inquisitive manner, without judgement. Nobody has to convince each other, you are all responsible for your own thoughts and emotions.

Take responsibility for your emotions as you are expressing them. The other person is not responsible for your feelings. You can take responsibility with sentences such as:

- I notice that when you say X, the following is happening to me: ...
- Are you open to examining together where this feeling is coming from?
- What does it make you feel when you hear what is happening to me?

If your emotion is too intense, ask for a time-out. Better a time-out than a conversation where you cannot listen to each other anymore.

We tend to fill in what someone else is thinking. We quickly form an image of someone and expect them to have certain opinions. Because of this we sometimes only partly listen and pick out those sentences that fit in with what we are expecting to hear.

The following things help you to listen actively and openly to the other person:

- **Ask open questions:**
 - What makes you say/feel X? (*What* often feels more neutral, than *why*)
 - You say X: can you tell me a bit more about that?

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- **Summarise to check whether you understood it correctly:**

- If I understand you correctly you. Do I summarise it well?

- **Ask about word choices that trigger a strong (positive or negative) emotion in you:**

- I notice that the word X evokes something in me. What exactly makes you use this word? What are your associations with this word?

- **Stay away from offering your own opinion.** There will be room for this later in the conversation. It is first about really 'meeting' and understanding the other person.

Also tell your participants that it does not matter if they accidentally ask closed or suggestive questions. Encourage them to respectfully correct each other.

It can be helpful to make a small handout with the questions and sentences around naming emotions and listening with an open mind.

2.2.2 Phase 2: Safe and open climate for discussion

In the introductory phase, you gave the group tools and a framework for a constructive and open discussion with each other. Then the conversation can begin.

As a moderator during this main phase of the meeting, you have the responsibility to stimulate and monitor the process. A safe climate for discussion is the shared responsibility of you and the group, but as the leader the final responsibility lies with you.

- Make sure that the person speaking is given the opportunity to tell their story.
- Tell your participants that it is important to let each other finish what they are saying.
- And that at the same time it is the speaker's responsibility not to monopolise the turn definitely.
- You can choose to give the above 'rules of the game' in your own words to the group during the introductory phase. In this way, everyone knows in advance what is needed for a good conversation and what is expected in this setting.
- If someone asks a closed or suggestive question, invite them to reformulate the question.
- Be alert to non-verbal expressions from listeners: rolling their eyes, demonstrative sighing, a sound of irritation. Your own feelings can guide you as to whether, and if so how to react so that it invites and, where necessary, 'corrects' the other person:
 - Name what you see/hear without interpreting:
 - *Do not:* I can see that you are irritated by what is being said.
 - *Do:* I can see you rolling your eyes. Do you want to share what makes you do that?

2.2.3 Phase 3: Feeling 'seen and heard' on going home

Make sure you end the session with a central conversation in a positive manner:

- State that it is important that everyone goes home with a good feeling, that nothing will linger negatively.
- Tell them that if some emotions are still lingering, you would very much like to hear it: preferably now, within the group, so that you can still respond to it.
- Indicate that it is always possible to react afterwards. For example, if someone at home still feels that some emotions are lingering. Or if someone does not feel safe enough to share it in the group. Indicate how they can get in touch: by email, a sticky note, etc.
- If something is mentioned, the challenge for you as a moderator is to deal with it in a good way with the group without having to redo/re-start the whole discussion.
- Finally, thank all participants for their openness and courage: it takes courage to open up to others and to make yourself vulnerable!

ANNEX 5: HOW TO EMOTION NETWORK**2.2.4 Your emotions as a discussion leader**

It is good to realise that you can also be moved yourself as a discussion leader. Somebody may say something that you yourself feel angry about, for example. Or you are annoyed by a dominant participant in the group. Below are a number of tools for dealing with this.

- Regarding the topics, check in advance how you yourself relate to it. What are your emotional triggers? Talk about them with your partner, friends, family, or colleagues so that you can remove the sharp edges.
- Are you annoyed by a participant? Be aware of it. By being aware of them, you take a part of the load off. By approaching this participant with open language you invite yourself to act without letting your emotion guide you.
- Does what happens during the discussion really get to you? Express this, do not clench to neutrality, your participants will notice that. Do not make it bigger than it is. Indicate in your own words 'I notice that I am feeling angry/sad/frustrated'. This openness can lead to a good conversation. Be in control, do not become a participant instead of a discussion leader. Here too you adhere to your own rules of an open attitude, open questions, etc.
- Is a discussion getting out of hand and are you noticing that you are no longer in control? Involve the group in the solution (depending on the atmosphere in the group). Ask the group the question: What is needed to make this discussion feel open and safe again? Or put the discussion on hold for a moment and take a short break. Retreat during the break and find out how you want to proceed.